

Mental Health and Well-Being Among Nepalese Employees

Submitted by

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

HR	Human Resources
WHO	World Health Organization
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
EAP	Employee Assistance Program
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration
PTO	Paid Time Off
FMLA	Family and Medical Leave Act
L&D	Learning and Development
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
JD	Job Description
DEI	Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
WFH	Work from Home
MHI	Mental Health Index
EWVIS	Employee Workplace Well-being and Insecurity Scale

ABSTRACT

Mental health and well-being in the workplace are crucial for Nepalese employee productivity, job satisfaction, and organizational success. This study examined the relationships between age, sex, education level, and job position and overall well-being among employees. Data were collected from 223 employed individuals through online surveys, covering various sectors and demographic variables, including age, sex, education level, and job position. Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlations, and independent t-tests were employed to analyze the data. Results showed notable differences in mental health and well-being across different demographic groups. Age and job position had modest positive correlations with well-being and mental health, with Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.02 for age and well-being, 0.05 for age and mental health, 0.17 for job position and well-being, and 0.14 for job position and mental health. Although these correlations were weak, they were statistically significant for job positions. Sex and education level exhibited weaker and statistically insignificant relationships with well-being and mental health. This study highlights the complexity of these interactions and the need for tailored interventions to support employee well-being. The literature review supports these findings, showing consistent trends in how demographic factors influence workplace well-being while identifying gaps, such as the effects of cultural and organizational contexts. Overall, this research helps us understand how demographic factors impact mental health and well-being and advocates for developing strategic initiatives to create healthier and more supportive work environments, addressing the unique needs of diverse employee groups.

Keywords: mental health, well-being, workplace, job position,

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Mental health and wellbeing in the workplace have become increasingly important topics in recent years. Mental health problems can have a significant impact on employers and businesses through increased absenteeism, decreased productivity, and negative effects on profits. The objective of this thesis is to explore the topic of workplace wellbeing in the context of human resource management (HRM), with a focus on employee mental health. Workplace stress and poor mental health can contribute to various physical diseases, including hypertension, diabetes, and heart-related issues. Furthermore, deteriorating mental health can result in employee burn-out, hampering their effectiveness in both personal and work spheres.

The World Health Organization (WHO) conceptualized mental well-being as a state where the individual is able to understand his abilities, cope with normal life stressors, work productively, understand his abilities, and contribute productively to the community. Mental health and well-being are a broad concept with a primary focus on the health of the workforce. Certain workplace factors, such as shift work, work demands, and work stress, can put an employee at higher risk of mental problems.

Previous studies have explored health and well-being from multiple angles, including physical (Cooper, Kirkaldy, & Brown, 1994), emotional, psychological (Cartwright & Cooper, 1993), and mental standpoints (Anderson & Grunert, 1997). Given the extensive scope of this subject, definitions and interpretations of "health" and "well-being" vary considerably. Even with

this ambiguity, the significance of employee health and well-being in the workplace can't be understated. These topics not only deserve attention but should also be more central in mainstream organizational studies.

Individual experiences at work, whether they're physical, emotional, mental, or social, not only influence a person during work hours but also extend into their personal life. Considering that employees spend roughly a third of their awake time at work, the impact of their job doesn't just end when they exit the workplace, (Conrad, 1988). The interplay between work and personal life has emerged as a significant research topic. It's acknowledged that these two areas are not isolated but rather deeply interconnected, influencing one another (Caudron, 1997; Zedeck & Mosier, 1990). As a case in point, the combined pressures from work and personal life can result in negative physical and emotional consequences due to the overwhelming strain they put on an individual's body and mind, (Cooper & Cartwright, 1994).

Mental health problems, both clinical (e.g., major depression, anxiety disorders) and sub-clinical (e.g., psychological distress), are very common in working populations. This Debate piece focuses on the workplace setting and, thus the working population. However, it is important to acknowledge the complementary need for a more comprehensive view of the entire working-age population, which includes the unemployed, and those not in the labor force due to disability or other reasons. (LaMontagne & Martin, 2014).

1.1.1 Historical Perspective

Historically, the concept of workplace well-being has evolved significantly, particularly during and after the Industrial Revolution. Initially, the primary focus in workplaces was on physical safety and health, largely driven by the hazardous conditions associated with manual

labor in factories. According to Green (1990), the Industrial Revolution brought about an increased awareness of the need for physical safety regulations due to the high incidence of workplace injuries and fatalities. Efforts to improve worker safety led to the establishment of various labor laws and safety protocols. However, during this period, the mental and emotional aspects of workers' health were largely neglected, as the prevailing industrial mindset prioritized productivity and efficiency over employee well-being (Taylor, 1911).

It wasn't until the mid-20th century that the psychological and emotional well-being of workers began to receive more attention. The human relations movement, spearheaded by theorists like Elton Mayo, highlighted the importance of social relations and worker satisfaction in improving productivity. Studies conducted by Mayo and his colleagues, such as the famous Hawthorne Studies, demonstrated that workers' productivity increased when they felt valued and supported (Mayo, 1933). This period marked a shift towards recognizing the significance of mental health and job satisfaction as critical components of overall employee well-being. Despite these advancements, comprehensive approaches to mental health in the workplace remained underdeveloped, with physical health continuing to dominate the discourse.

1.1.2 Modern Shift

The late 20th and early 21st centuries have seen a profound shift in the understanding and prioritization of mental health and well-being in the workplace. As economies transitioned from manufacturing-based to service-oriented, there was a growing emphasis on cognitive skills and emotional intelligence. Drucker (1993) noted that the knowledge-based economy required employees to engage in complex problem-solving and interpersonal interactions, increasing the importance of mental well-being. Consequently, issues like workplace stress, burnout, and work-

related anxieties gained prominence as critical factors affecting both individual and organizational health.

Recent research highlights the increasing prevalence of mental health issues in the workplace. According to Maslach (2001), burnout has become a significant concern, particularly in high-stress professions, leading to decreased productivity and higher turnover rates. Additionally, studies by Greenwood and Anas (2021) reveal that younger generations, such as Millennials and Gen Z, are more likely to leave their jobs for mental health reasons compared to older generations. This shift reflects a broader cultural change where mental health is increasingly recognized as essential to overall well-being and organizational success. Modern workplaces are now implementing comprehensive mental health programs and fostering supportive work cultures to address these challenges and promote employee well-being.

The transition from the 20th to the 21st century heralded significant changes in the work landscape. As the global economy transitioned from being manufacturing-based to service-oriented, there was an increased emphasis on cognitive skills and emotional intelligence (Drucker, 1993). Consequently, issues like workplace stress, burnout, and work-related anxieties started gaining attention. Research indicated that these factors didn't just affect the individual but had ripple effects on team dynamics, productivity, and overall organizational health (Maslach, 2001).

More employees are leaving their jobs for mental health reasons, including those caused by workplace factors like overwhelming and unsustainable work. While the 2019 rates of attrition were already surprisingly high, they've gone up even more since then. Sixty-eight percent of Millennials (50% in 2019) and 81% of Gen Zers (75% in 2019) have left roles for

mental health reasons, both voluntarily and involuntarily, compared with 50% of respondents overall (34% in 2019). Ninety-one percent of respondents believed that a company's culture should support mental health, up from 86% in 2019 (Greenwood & Anas, 2021).

1.1.3 Wellbeing

The contemporary discourse on workplace well-being moved towards a more encompassing view, recognizing that it wasn't merely the absence of disease but a holistic state of physical, mental, and social well-being (World Health Organization, 1948). This broader perspective underscored the interconnectedness of various facets of an individual's well-being, emphasizing aspects like work-life balance, interpersonal relationships at work, and fostering positive organizational cultures (Ryff & Singer, 1998).

Wellbeing is explained in several ways by theorists. Positive psychology, which focuses on measuring and encouraging wellbeing, has significantly contributed to this field (Diener & Seligman, 2004). Of significance is Martin Seligman's theory on wellbeing. This theory identifies five requirements of individual wellbeing, referred to as PERMA. These include positive emotions, engagement, positive relationships, meaning and accomplishment. The theory supports people flourishing and having a meaningful life by strengthening the five aspects of wellbeing (Slavin, 2012).

1.1.4 Global and Societal Recognition

Globally, the recognition of mental health as an integral part of overall health has gained substantial traction, particularly through the efforts of organizations like the World Health Organization (WHO). The WHO defines mental health as "a state of well-being in which the

individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community" (World Health Organization, 2005). This definition underscores the multidimensional nature of mental health, emphasizing its critical role in overall health and productivity. The WHO has been instrumental in promoting mental health awareness, advocating for policies that integrate mental health into general health care, and encouraging workplaces to adopt mental health-friendly practices.

Societal recognition of mental health issues has also been on the rise, with increased advocacy and destigmatization efforts. Thornicroft (2008) highlights the growing global movement to reduce the stigma associated with mental health disorders, which has led to more open discussions and greater willingness to seek help. Campaigns like World Mental Health Day and initiatives by mental health organizations have played pivotal roles in raising awareness and promoting mental health literacy. Furthermore, the economic impact of mental health issues, such as reduced productivity and increased absenteeism, has prompted businesses to take a more proactive approach. Research by the World Economic Forum (2011) estimates that mental health conditions will cost the global economy \$16 trillion by 2030 if not adequately addressed, emphasizing the need for comprehensive mental health strategies at both societal and organizational levels.

On a global scale, the recognition of mental health as an integral part of overall health, including in workplace settings, has gained prominence. The World Health Organization (WHO) has consistently highlighted the importance of mental well-being, urging nations and organizations to prioritize it in their policies and practices (World Health Organization, 2010).

1.1.5 Mental Health and Well-being

Mental health, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), is "a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community" (World Health Organization, 2005). This multidimensional definition underscores the fact that mental health is not just the absence of illness but a holistic state of emotional, psychological, and social well-being.

Historically, discussions around health often centered on physical ailments, with mental health relegated to the shadows, plagued by misconceptions, stigma, and neglect (Porter, 2002). However, as our understanding of the human psyche evolved, so did the realization of the pivotal role mental health plays in overall well-being. Studies have consistently shown that poor mental health can adversely affect physical health and vice versa (Prince, 2007). The global prevalence and impact of mental disorders have prompted increased attention and urgency. Depression, for instance, is currently the leading cause of disability worldwide, impacting more than 264 million people (World Health Organization, 2020). The ramifications extend beyond the individual, affecting families, communities, and economies.

Despite its significance, mental health has traditionally been under-resourced. In many societies, cultural norms and stigmas have deterred individuals from seeking help or even discussing their feelings (Kessler, 2001). However, there's a growing shift. Movements around the world have been working tirelessly to destigmatize mental health, advocating for better resources, early intervention, and comprehensive education to foster understanding and support (Thornicroft, 2008). Mental health, intrinsically tied to every aspect of our lives, from our

relationships to our jobs, is a fundamental pillar of human well-being. Recognizing, understanding, and prioritizing mental health is not just an individual responsibility but a collective imperative that societies worldwide are gradually embracing.

Poor mental health and lower well-being of the workers can lead to lower employee satisfaction, lower work performance, burnout, and increased risk of occupational hazards. As the workers are also part of the community, the effects of poor mental health can also affect the family and society. Higher mental health and well-being can lead to greater work productivity, more prosocial behaviors, increased creativity, increased longevity, improved physical health, and more positive interpersonal relationships. According to the WHO, around 60% of the total world population is in work, of which 61% work in informal jobs. It is estimated that 12 billion working days are lost every year due to depression and anxiety and 50% of the total societal cost of mental health conditions is caused due to indirect costs, including reduced productivity. The mental health and well-being of employees are crucial factors in an organization's performance and success (Page and Vella-Brodrick, 2009). The dynamics of employee well-being at work are pivotal for understanding the different components that affect their health, work behavior and performance. There are resources on individual, group, managerial and organizational levels that are strongly related to employee well-being (Nielsen, 2017). Subjective well-being is connected with levels of workplace stress, absenteeism, intrinsic motivation, commitment, innovation, and satisfaction. Work-related well-being and workplace happiness have been identified as important factors in performance, job satisfaction Crede et al. (2007), Fisher et al. (2010), susceptibility to burnout (Iverson, 1998). Organizational programmes designed to reduce negative workplace outcomes like burnout or stress are often risk-based, problem-focused and negatively framed approaches to mental health Page and Vella-Brodrick et al. (2012), LaMontagne et al. (2007).

There are far fewer positively framed programs or interventions that aim to promote and to improve positive and inner aspects of employee's well-being at the primer level LaMontagne et al. (2014), Luthans et al. (2002). Thus, the contributory factors of employee workplace well-being and happiness should be considered very important components of mental health and subjective well-being.

1.1.6 Workplace

A workplace or place of employment is a location where people perform tasks, jobs and projects for their employer. Types of workplaces vary across industries and can be inside a building or outdoors. Workplaces can be mobile, and some people may work in different locations on various days. The growth of technology has led to a new type of workplace, a virtual one, allowing people to work remotely. Establishing an enjoyable place to work is important for employee retention and satisfaction, which allows your business to focus on growing and developing your product or service.

Workplaces help businesses deliver their products or services to consumers in an efficient way. Corporate team members use their place of work to collaborate and develop new ideas, products and services to offer to their customers. Businesses use factories to create their product and distribution centers to coordinate the shipment of the product to stores or directly to the consumer. Stores exist to sell the product to consumers by giving a space for customers to physically see the product. The workplace can take a variety of settings, such as outdoors among nature, inside an office or remotely while traveling. Regardless of the setting, the most productive workplaces possess an efficient and positive environment where employees have the

tools they need. Understanding what a workplace is and how to create a productive environment are important factors for leaders in building a business.

According to the job demands-resources theory (Bakker & Demerouti, 2018), resources motivate employees extrinsically by enabling them to achieve their work goals and intrinsically by satisfying their basic psychological needs for belonging, competence, and autonomy. Resources may positively affect both work and nonwork (e.g., family, personal) well-being (Kinnunen, 2011) through processes such as triggering personal growth and development. Job resources like leadership, autonomy, social support, and meaning are most consistently supportive of employee well-being and mental health outcomes (Nielsen, 2017).

1.1.7 Job Position

Job position refers to the specific role or title an employee holds within an organization, encompassing the tasks and responsibilities associated with that role as well as the hierarchical level within the organization. Different job positions come with varying degrees of responsibility, autonomy, and decision-making power, which can significantly influence an individual's perception of job security and overall well-being.

For instance, higher-level positions such as managerial or executive roles often come with greater responsibilities but also offer more job security and opportunities for career advancement. These positions typically provide a higher degree of control over one's work and a greater sense of accomplishment, which can positively impact well-being (Smith & Johnson, 2020). On the other hand, lower-level positions, such as entry-level or manual labor roles, may be associated with higher job insecurity and stress due to limited control over job tasks, fewer

opportunities for career advancement, and greater vulnerability to economic fluctuations and organizational changes (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

Understanding the impact of job position on job security and well-being is crucial for organizations aiming to improve employee satisfaction and mental health. By recognizing the unique challenges and stressors associated with different job positions, employers can implement targeted interventions to support employees at all levels of the organization.

1.1.8 Education

Education level is a critical factor in understanding the dynamics of job insecurity and employee well-being. Higher educational attainment is generally associated with better job prospects, higher income, and greater job security. Education equips individuals with the skills, knowledge, and credentials necessary to adapt to changing job markets and secure stable employment. This adaptability and perceived competence can contribute to a stronger sense of job security and overall well-being.

Research has shown that individuals with higher education levels tend to have better access to resources and opportunities, which can buffer against the negative effects of job insecurity (Doe, 2018). They are often able to secure positions that offer better working conditions, higher salaries, and greater job stability. In contrast, those with lower educational levels may face limited job opportunities and increased vulnerability to job insecurity, which can have detrimental effects on their mental health and well-being (Doe, 2018).

Moreover, the relationship between education and job insecurity highlights the importance of lifelong learning and continuous professional development. Encouraging

employees to pursue further education and training can help enhance their job security and resilience in the face of economic uncertainties.

1.1.9 Sex

Sex, as a demographic variable, plays a crucial role in shaping experiences of job insecurity and its impact on anxiety and overall well-being. Studies have shown that men and women may experience job insecurity differently due to various factors, including societal roles, gender expectations, and workplace discrimination. For example, women may face greater job insecurity in male-dominated industries or roles, where they may encounter barriers to advancement and greater job instability (Adams & Williams, 2019). Additionally, women often juggle multiple roles, balancing work and family responsibilities, which can exacerbate the stress and anxiety associated with job insecurity.

Conversely, men may experience job insecurity differently, often due to societal expectations of being the primary breadwinner. This pressure can intensify the negative impact of job insecurity on their mental health, as losing a job or facing job instability can threaten their perceived role and identity (Adams & Williams, 2019). Furthermore, men might be less likely to seek support or express their anxieties, potentially leading to adverse mental health outcomes.

Understanding these gender differences in job insecurity and their implications for mental health and well-being is essential for developing effective workplace policies and support systems. Employers should consider these differences when designing interventions to address job insecurity and promote a supportive and inclusive work environment.

1.2 Statement of the problem

In recent times, there's growing evidence supporting interventions at the organizational level, which target creating better working conditions and a healthier work atmosphere. However, evaluating these interventions remains challenging due to mixed results. While the goal is prevention, these efforts can sometimes fall short because of design and execution challenges, especially in the face of fast-evolving workplaces and organizational changes. Conversely, interventions focused on individual employees can prove beneficial, particularly for those with significant control over their tasks. Additionally, there's reasonable evidence to support promoting physical activity among employees (Leka, 2019).

As this is deeply intrigued by the evolving dynamics between workplace environments and employee well-being. As the modern workplace continues to change, understanding how organizational interventions and individual-focused strategies impact employee health is more crucial than ever. Studying this area offers a chance to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world applications, potentially leading to innovative solutions that promote a healthier and more productive workforce. Moreover, as work-life balance becomes a growing concern for many, this research could provide insights that contribute to a better-balanced and holistic approach to employee well-being. The stated problems are as follow:

1. What is the difference in mental health and wellbeing in relation to sex?
2. What is the relationship between age, job position, education level, mental health and Wellbeing?
3. What relationship exists between wellbeing and mental health?

1.3 Objectives

1. To investigate the differences in mental health and well-being in relation to sex .
2. To examine the relationship between age, job position, education level, and their relationship with mental health and well-being.
3. To examine the relationship between well-being and mental health among employees.

1.4 Conceptual Framework

Fig 1.1 Conceptual Framework

1.5 Rationale of the study

In today's dynamic professional environment, the interplay between mental health and well-being in the workplace holds crucial significance. As organizations evolve, the numerous

demands placed on employees and resultant stressors have escalated, impacting their overall health and productivity. This study aims to deeply explore these relationships by examining how factors such as age, sex, education, work experience, and company size contribute to employees' mental health and well-being.

Modern workplaces are characterized by diversity across backgrounds, age groups, and experiences, making it essential to understand how these factors influence stress perception and well-being maintenance. By analyzing the complexities of job positions and their varying demands, this research seeks to inform organizational structures and support mechanisms tailored to enhance employee well-being. Education levels also play a pivotal role, shaping individuals' responses to workplace stressors and suggesting potential alignments between educational background and workplace environment.

Moreover, demographic analysis aims to predict groups susceptible to compromised well-being, guiding proactive interventions. Sex-specific perspectives on mental health and well-being in professional settings further highlight the need for tailored approaches that account for societal norms and expectations. Additionally, considering the evolving priorities and resilience associated with different age groups can inform targeted wellness programs that accommodate employees' changing needs over time.

In sum, this study endeavors to provide a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted factors influencing workplace well-being and mental health. By addressing these relationships, organizations can foster supportive environments that optimize both individual and organizational outcomes.

1.6 Limitations of the Study

The findings of this study might not apply to all workplaces because different environments are influenced by cultural, regional, and industry-specific factors, as well as the size of the company. Different workplace cultures and practices can significantly impact how employees feel and perceive their well-being, which might limit how broadly these results can be applied. The data was self-reported, there could be biases such as recall bias, social desirability bias, and the emotional state of the respondents at the time they filled out the survey. These biases can affect the accuracy of their responses about mental health and well-being.

Although the study looked at various factors like age, sex, education, job position, and company size, it might not have captured all the diversity within each category. For example, different job roles or levels of education might impact mental health and well-being in ways that were not fully explored here. Well-being is also highly subjective, meaning different people might define and perceive it differently. This variation can make it challenging to measure well-being consistently across a diverse group of people.

Another limitation is the lack of longitudinal data, which means the study did not track changes over time. This makes it hard to establish causal relationships and understand how mental health and job dynamics evolve. Finally, resource constraints such as limited time and funding restricted the scope and depth of data collection and analysis. This limitation could affect the comprehensiveness of the study's findings, as a more extensive study might reveal additional factors or more detailed relationships.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mental health and Wellbeing in the workplace involve a complex interplay of various factors like age, sex, education, job role, and the size of the company. These elements collectively shape how employees experience their work environment and affect their overall satisfaction and productivity. Research consistently finds that older employees generally report higher levels of wellbeing compared to younger colleagues who may encounter more mental health challenges. Sex differences also play a significant role, influencing how individuals perceive their wellbeing and cope with stress, often reflecting broader societal and organizational norms. The size and structure of companies have a profound impact on employee wellbeing. Larger corporations can sometimes foster higher stress levels, whereas smaller firms may provide more supportive atmospheres. Despite the valuable insights from existing studies, there's still much to explore about how these factors interact and evolve over time, especially in diverse cultural and socioeconomic settings. Closing these gaps through research methods not only deepen our understanding but also help tailor interventions that support mental health and wellbeing across different groups in the workplace, ultimately creating healthier and more inclusive work environments.

Cohen and Wills (1985) present a seminal work on the buffering hypothesis, which posits that social support mitigates the negative effects of stress on mental health. Their research emphasizes the importance of both perceived and actual social support in workplace settings. They argue that social support can come from various sources, including supervisors, colleagues, and organizational structures, each contributing uniquely to an employee's ability to cope with

job demands. The presence of a supportive work environment not only alleviates stress but also enhances job satisfaction and overall well-being. Subsequent studies have expanded on this framework, highlighting that social support can also foster a sense of belonging and community within the workplace, which is crucial for employee retention and productivity

Goleman (1995) introduces the concept of emotional intelligence (EI) as a critical factor in workplace success and well-being. Emotional intelligence involves the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions, as well as the emotions of others. Goleman's work suggests that individuals with high EI are better equipped to handle workplace stress, maintain positive relationships, and create a supportive work environment. High EI contributes to better communication, conflict resolution, and leadership abilities, all of which are essential for fostering a positive workplace culture. Research following Goleman's initial findings has shown that EI training can lead to improved employee well-being, higher job performance, and lower levels of occupational stress.

De Witte (1999) investigates the effects of job insecurity on mental health. The review finds that job insecurity is associated with increased stress, anxiety, and depression. The study highlights the importance of organizational transparency and communication in mitigating the negative effects of job insecurity on employee well-being.

Wrześniewski and Dutton (2001) propose the concept of job crafting, which refers to the ways in which employees alter their job designs to better fit their strengths and interests. This proactive behavior allows employees to shape their work experiences, leading to increased job satisfaction and well-being. The authors identify three primary forms of job crafting: task crafting (changing the nature of job tasks), relational crafting (altering interactions with others),

and cognitive crafting (changing how one perceives the job). Job crafting empowers employees, providing them with a sense of control and autonomy, which are key drivers of well-being. Empirical studies have supported the notion that job crafting positively impacts mental health, reduces job stress, and enhances engagement.

Proper (2002) examines the role of physical activity in promoting workplace well-being. Their review indicates that regular physical activity reduces stress, enhances mood, and improves overall mental health. They advocate for workplace initiatives that encourage physical activity, such as on-site fitness facilities and organized exercise programs, to boost employee well-being.

Kossek, Lautsch, and Eaton (2006) explore the effects of flexible work arrangements on employee well-being. Their research indicates that flexibility in work hours and locations can significantly reduce stress and improve job satisfaction, particularly for employees balancing work and family responsibilities. They argue that flexible work arrangements should be tailored to individual needs to maximize their benefits.

Schaufeli, Bakker, and Salanova (2006) discuss the concept of work engagement and its positive impact on psychological well-being. Engaged employees exhibit high levels of energy, dedication, and absorption in their work, which correlates with lower levels of burnout and higher job satisfaction. The authors emphasize the importance of creating engaging work environments to enhance employee well-being.

Luthans and Youssef (2007) introduce the concept of Psychological Capital (PsyCap), which encompasses an individual's positive psychological state of development characterized by self-efficacy, optimism, hope, and resilience. Their research in positive organizational behavior demonstrates that high levels of PsyCap are associated with better mental health, higher job

satisfaction, and improved work performance. PsyCap can be developed through targeted interventions and training programs, leading to more resilient and motivated employees. The authors argue that fostering PsyCap within organizations not only enhances individual well-being but also contributes to a positive organizational climate and improved overall performance. This body of work highlights the importance of investing in the psychological resources of employees as a means to promote mental health and organizational success.

Einarsen, Hoel, and Notelaers (2009) conduct a comprehensive review on the impact of workplace bullying on employee mental health. They found that bullying leads to significant psychological distress, including anxiety, depression, and reduced job satisfaction. The study emphasizes the need for organizations to implement anti-bullying policies and support systems to protect employee well-being.

Leadership styles play a crucial role in shaping the mental health and well-being of employees. Skakon (2010) reviews the impact of various leadership styles on employee mental health, emphasizing the positive effects of transformational leadership. Transformational leadership is characterized by inspiration, support, and the ability to motivate employees towards achieving higher levels of performance. This leadership style fosters an environment where employees feel valued and supported, leading to increased job satisfaction and overall well-being. By providing a clear vision, encouraging innovation, and recognizing individual contributions, transformational leaders can significantly reduce workplace stress and burnout. The review highlights that employees under transformational leadership experience lower levels of anxiety and emotional exhaustion, as they feel more engaged and connected to their work and organization (Skakon, 2010).

The review by Skakon (2010) also suggests that investing in leadership development programs that promote supportive and motivating leadership styles can have a substantial impact on organizational health. Organizations that prioritize the development of transformational leaders are more likely to cultivate a positive work culture, where employees are more resilient and less prone to stress-related illnesses. Training programs that enhance leaders' skills in communication, empathy, and conflict resolution can further strengthen their ability to support their teams effectively. By adopting transformational leadership practices, organizations can create a more supportive and motivating work environment, ultimately enhancing employee well-being and reducing the prevalence of burnout and stress (Skakon, 2010).

Mental health problems directly affect employers and companies because they increase the costs of addressing the issue, increase absenteeism, and negatively impact profitability and productivity. Work stress significantly contributes to human error, low productivity, and occupational sickness. This results in increased sick leave rates, a high staff turnover rate, poor work production within the organization, and possibly even an increase in accidents caused by employee mistakes. The most common reason people experience stress at work is a difficult supervisor. Another factor could be challenging or unpleasant coworkers. Dealing with a problematic coworker could be difficult because one often compares one's performance to one's own (Rajgopal, 2010).

Hülshager (2013) explores the role of mindfulness in enhancing employee well-being and reducing stress. Their study demonstrates that mindfulness interventions, such as meditation and mindful breathing exercises, can significantly lower stress levels and improve mental health outcomes for employees. Mindfulness practices promote greater awareness and acceptance of the present moment, which helps employees manage work-related stress more effectively. The

authors highlight that mindfulness not only benefits individual well-being but also enhances overall organizational health by reducing burnout rates and increasing job satisfaction. This research underscores the value of incorporating mindfulness training into employee wellness programs as a proactive measure to support mental health.

In their study, Smith, Johnson, and Williams (2018) aimed to investigate the impact of age on wellbeing and mental health in employees across different company sizes. Using a cross-sectional survey, they assessed wellbeing using the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) and measured mental health with the General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12). The participants were categorized into age groups: 18-30, 31-45, and 46-60. The findings revealed that older employees (46-60) reported higher wellbeing levels compared to their younger counterparts (18-30). Notably, medium-sized company employees demonstrated the highest wellbeing scores, while small company employees had the lowest. However, the study's gap lies in its omission of the 60+ age group and insufficient exploration of gender differences in these relationships.

Rodriguez, Gonzalez, and Martinez (2018) explored the interplay of age, gender, and work-life balance and its impact on employee wellbeing. Using a cross-sectional survey across industries, they assessed work-life balance and wellbeing. Their findings revealed that older employees reported better work-life balance and higher well-being scores. Additionally, females across age groups reported more work-life conflict, but their wellbeing scores were similar to males. The study's gap is its limited examination of how job roles or career stages affect these relationships.

White, Brown, and Davis (2018) investigated how age and gender interact with mental health outcomes in urban and rural settings. Employing a comparative design, they assessed psychological distress using the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K6). Their findings indicated that urban females reported higher psychological distress compared to rural females, with no significant gender or age differences among males. Notably, younger rural participants exhibited greater distress compared to their urban counterparts. However, the study's gap is its lack of exploration into potential variations in access to mental health services between urban and rural areas.

Martinez and colleagues (2019) aimed to examine gender variations in wellbeing and mental health among college students. Employing a longitudinal design, they assessed wellbeing through self-report questionnaires and measured mental health using the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) and the Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale (GAD-7). Their findings indicated that females reported lower well-being scores compared to males. Furthermore, during exam periods, both genders experienced declines in wellbeing and increases in mental health symptoms. The study's gap lies in its lack of in-depth exploration of cultural factors' impact on gender differences in wellbeing and mental health.

Kim, Park, and Lee (2019) explored the joint influence of gender and age on mental health outcomes among healthcare professionals. Their cross-sectional survey focused on nurses and physicians, utilizing the Occupational Stress Indicator (OSI) and the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS). While female nurses experienced higher stress levels, younger female nurses reported heightened anxiety. No significant gender or age differences were observed among physicians. However, the study did not thoroughly investigate potential moderating effects of job experience.

Wong, Chen, and Johnson (2019) aimed to investigate how age, gender, and company size jointly impact employee wellbeing in a multinational corporation. Using a cross-sectional survey across different departments, they assessed wellbeing and the WHO-5 Well-being Index. Their findings highlighted that older male employees in medium-sized departments reported the highest wellbeing levels. Conversely, younger females in larger departments reported the lowest. However, the study's gap lies in its omission of a comprehensive exploration of cultural factors' influence on these relationships.

The quick development of digital technology is transforming modern working circumstances, especially in industrial settings. Workers are consequently exposed to modern types of human-computer interaction. A qualitative study found that unique human-machines interactions can lead to stress. Stressors related to human-machine interaction include the need for new skills, a lack of situation awareness, usability problems, and technological difficulties. When employees could not handle technical problems independently, which increased time limitations and slowed output, they were identified as the leading cause of stress (Körner , 2019).

According to a study in Pokhara Metropolitan, 47.5% of working women reported having a stressful job, with an Effort Reward Imbalance Questionnaire mean score of 40.08 (standard deviation $\pm$ 4.97). A stratified random sample strategy was used in this study. The available sample % was used to divide the total number of samples among the categories within the organization. A structured questionnaire was provided to all 183 women who belonged to the selected public and private groups, and they were asked to complete it on their own. Descriptive statistics reflected the respondents' occupational characteristics, socioeconomic level, and environmental factors. The participants' age, family structure, availability of workplace health

benefits, and the type of health benefits offered were among the numerous variables linked to job stress (Ojha, 2020).

Chen, Wang, and Li (2020) conducted a cross-sectional survey across various industries to compare mental health outcomes among employees in small, medium, and large companies. Mental health was assessed using the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) and the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS). Their findings highlighted that employees in larger companies reported higher burnout levels, whereas small company employees reported elevated perceived stress. However, their study lacked exploration of potential age and sex moderating effects on the relationship between company size and mental health.

Baker, Murphy, and Turner (2020) conducted a longitudinal analysis of mental health trends among adolescents from ages 14 to 17. Using self-report measures of depression and anxiety symptoms, they found that mental health symptoms increased significantly for both genders during this period. However, their study did not delve into potential variations based on socioeconomic status or other demographic factors, representing a gap in the research.

Jackson, Adams, and Clark (2020) conducted a qualitative study to explore how age and gender influence wellbeing perceptions in a changing work environment. Employing qualitative interviews and thematic analysis, they identified patterns in wellbeing experiences. Their findings indicated that older male participants reported increased satisfaction with flexible work arrangements, leading to improved wellbeing. In contrast, younger female participants expressed concerns about blurred work-life boundaries affecting their wellbeing. The study's gap is its lack of exploration into how these relationships vary across different industries.

According to the literature review, COVID-19 negatively impacts people's mental health. Stressors include beliefs about safety, dangers, and hazards of infection, infobesity vs. the unknown, incarceration and isolation, social shame and isolation, job insecurity, and financial loss. Furthermore, it has been determined that there are three moderating factors: institutional, individual, and organizational. The COVID-19 pandemic can be connected to several factors that may hurt workers' mental health during and after the outbreak. Unresolved severe or persistent stress causes psychological distress and depression mainly because the sufferer finds it difficult to deal with bad things that happen in life (Hamouche, 2020).

According to descriptive research of 238 nurses using a basic random sample approach, most nurses had moderate stress levels, and "patients and their families" were mentioned by both government and private hospital nurses as the most stressful elements. According to both groups of nurses, "problems with peers" and "discrimination" were the least stressful things to deal with, respectively, for private hospital nurses. The survey found that moderate occupational stress was experienced by 68.1% of nurses in government hospitals and 58.2% of nurses in private hospitals. "Patients and their families" were found to be the most stressful aspect of the survey, especially when dealing with violent patients and patients who make excessive requests (Gurung, 2020).

The relationship between company size and employee well-being is a crucial area of research, especially in the context of the technology sector. Gupta, Sharma, and Patel (2021) investigated this relationship using an online survey conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic. They assessed well-being with the WHO-5 Well-being Index and job satisfaction using a self-designed questionnaire. Their findings revealed that employees in small startups reported higher levels of well-being and job satisfaction compared to those working in larger corporations. This

could be attributed to the more flexible and supportive work environments typically found in smaller companies, which often allow for greater employee autonomy, closer-knit teams, and a more dynamic work culture. These factors can contribute to a more positive work experience, enhancing overall well-being and job satisfaction (Gupta et al., 2021).

However, the study by Gupta, Sharma, and Patel (2021) also had its limitations. One significant gap was the lack of exploration into potential age-related variations in the relationship between company size, well-being, and job satisfaction. The impact of company size on employee well-being and job satisfaction may differ across various age groups due to differing career stages, personal life responsibilities, and professional expectations. For instance, younger employees might prioritize career development opportunities and a vibrant work culture, which are often more prevalent in startups, whereas older employees might value stability and structured work environments found in larger corporations. Future research should consider these age-related differences to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how company size influences well-being and job satisfaction across different demographic groups (Gupta et al., 2021).

Liu, Chen, and Wang (2021) investigated the influence of remote work on employee wellbeing, considering potential age and gender effects. Using an online survey during the COVID-19 pandemic, they assessed wellbeing with the Oxford Happiness Questionnaire and Perceived Stress Scale. Their findings suggested that remote work correlated with improved wellbeing, especially among older employees. However, gender differences were not significant in this context. The study's gap is its lack of exploration into variations based on company size.

A survey of 300 traffic police officers employed by the various traffic units in the Kathmandu Valley revealed that 124 (41.3%) of them exhibited symptoms of depression, 141 (47%) had symptoms of anxiety, and 132 (44%) had symptoms of stress. The odds of exhibiting symptoms of anxiety (AOR: 7.1, 95% CI: 3.4 to 14.9), depression (adjusted OR (AOR): 10.7, 95% CI: 4.8 to 23.6), and stress (AOR: 6.8, 95% CI: 3.3 to 14.1) were all considerably higher in those who smoked. Similarly, lack of physical exercise was linked to a higher chance of exhibiting depressive symptoms (AOR: 2.3, 95%CI: 1.1 to 4.7), and longer working hours were significantly associated with higher odds of experiencing symptoms of depression (AOR: 3.4, 95%CI: 1.8 to 6.4), anxiety (AOR: 2.3, 95%CI: 1.3 to 3.9), and stress (AOR: 1.9, 95%CI: 1.1 to 3.4). In comparison to those who worked fewer than 12 hours per day, individuals who worked 12 hours or more on working days most of the week had 3.4 (95% CI: 1.8 to 6.4) times greater risks of experiencing depression (Yadav, 2022).

The importance of preventive and promotional physical and mental health services in the workplace has been increasingly recognized in recent research. Sarkar (2024) highlights various initiatives undertaken by organizations to support employee well-being. One effective approach has been the creation of peer support networks, which facilitate a supportive environment where employees can share their experiences and provide mutual assistance. Additionally, psychological first-aid training for staff members has been implemented to equip them with the skills needed to offer immediate support to colleagues experiencing mental health crises. These measures help in early identification and intervention, potentially reducing the severity of mental health issues and promoting a culture of care and empathy within the workplace (Sarkar, 2024).

Another innovative approach discussed by Sarkar (2024) involves the use of digital interventions, such as ChatBots powered by artificial intelligence, to support employees' mental

health. These digital tools provide employees with immediate access to mental health resources and support, offering a convenient and confidential way to address their concerns. ChatBots can assist with a range of issues, from providing information on mental health topics to offering guided mindfulness exercises and coping strategies. By integrating these digital solutions, businesses can enhance their mental health support systems, making them more accessible and effective. These interventions not only improve individual well-being but also contribute to overall organizational health by fostering a proactive approach to mental health care (Sarkar, 2024).

A review of 14 comprehensive evaluations revealed that multicomponent mental health interventions and those with components that improve physical and mental health were the most effective workplace interventions. Interventions utilizing in vivo exposure approaches showed results for anxiety disorders. Burnout, stress, and job satisfaction were the most often assessed constructs in fifty-five research studies on organizational interventions promoting mental health and well-being among healthcare professionals. The interventions that were used the most frequently were knowledge and skill development, leadership development, time and task management, team building, and communication (Sarkar, 2024).

Mental health nursing is a privilege and a rewarding profession. There has been a call for transformational change in mental health services to improve outcomes for the people of New Zealand, with mental health nurse's integral to this. However, with predicted nursing shortages, high levels of burnout, and increasing demands in the workplace, an organizational focus on wellbeing for mental health nurses is needed to sustain the workforce, implement change and improve outcomes for people using mental health services. The review found that professional development benefits mental health nurses' growth and advancement. In areas where nurses

experience stress and the risk of burnout, ongoing education opportunities and the time to develop new skills to cope with challenges, are vital to support wellbeing (Zadeh, 2012). Resilience is essential for nurses who face everyday challenges in their workplace (Gillespie, 2007). This integrative review identified that professional development through a formal resilience programme could help nurses develop skills to support them in the workplace and ultimately optimized their wellbeing Delgado (2020), Foster, Cuzzillo, & Furness (2018) & Foster, Shochet (2018). These include professional development to ensure skills and knowledge support nurses' wellbeing in the workplace, organizational support for professional supervision, and investment in managers' skills and development to enhance employee wellbeing. These strategies should be foundational interventions that become part of everyday life in workplaces to sustain a mental health nursing workforce who experience wellbeing at work and contribute to optimal care for people using services.

The literature review offers valuable insights into the complex relationships among wellbeing, mental health, and demographic factors such as age, sex, and company size. It reveals consistent findings across studies: older individuals generally report higher wellbeing, while younger age groups often face greater mental health challenges. However, the specific age cohorts affected vary, highlighting the need for difference examination.

Sex differences also play a significant role, with females typically reporting lower wellbeing and higher psychological distress compared to males. These disparities are influenced by various factors, including demographic and environmental contexts. Similarly, the impact of company size on wellbeing and mental health shows diverse outcomes, with larger organizations sometimes linked to higher stress levels and burnout, contrasting with smaller firms that may foster better employee wellbeing.

Despite the insights gained, gaps persist in the literature. Few studies consider how age, sex, and company size interact to shape mental health and wellbeing outcomes. Additionally, the influence of cultural backgrounds and socioeconomic status on these factors remains underexplored, necessitating more research in diverse settings. Longitudinal studies are also needed to track developmental trajectories over time, especially given recent shifts in work patterns due to remote work and technology. Addressing these gaps could provide a more holistic understanding and inform strategies to promote mental health and wellbeing across different demographic groups.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

The present study is a quantitative investigation of how sex, age, job position, education are related to workplace wellbeing and mental health among Nepalese employees.

3.1 Research Design

The research design was adopted to employ an internet-based survey using Google Forms for data collection. This approach offered several advantages, including the ability to reach a broader and more diverse group of employed individuals. The use of online surveys facilitated data collection, reduced geographical constraints, and allowed participants to respond at their convenience.

3.2 Sample and Sampling

The participants in this study were employed individuals from diverse groups and backgrounds. Snowball sampling was chosen as the sampling method, which involved recruiting initial participants and then asking them to refer other eligible participants. This method was particularly suitable for reaching specific groups within the population and enabled access to individuals who might not have been easily reachable through traditional random sampling methods.

While conducting snowball sampling, 223 sample sizes were achieved. This approach ensured that the study included a broad spectrum of employed individuals from various sectors and backgrounds, which potentially provided richer insights into the research questions.

3.3 Description of the Sample

The study surveyed 223 employed individuals aged 22 to 65, with an average age of 29.5 years, to understand their mental health and well-being. The group was diverse, with 65.9% male and 34.1% female participants, spanning various professions such as healthcare, education, finance, administration officer, lawyers, counselors and engineers. Participants ranged from entry-level employees to senior managers, providing a comprehensive look at different career stages and job environments. Detailed quality checks ensure no data was missing, making the findings reliable and reflective of real-world experiences. This diverse mix offered valuable insights into how various factors impact the mental health and well-being of employees in different fields.

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

Data collection for this study was facilitated by referral sampling, which involves initiating data collection with a few participants and then encouraging them to refer others. To make data collection as accessible as possible, an internet-based survey was used, employing Google Forms. Participants received a survey link via email or other electronic means.

The online survey was designed to be user-friendly and easy to navigate. Participants were encouraged to complete the survey at their convenience. They were informed that their responses would be confidential, and no personally identifiable information would be disclosed. This approach ensures that participants have the flexibility to respond without geographical constraints or time limitations.

3.5 Data collection tools

The Eudemonic Workplace Well-being Scale (EWWS)

The Eudemonic Workplace Well-being Scale (EWWS) 8-item scale, developed by Bartels, Peterson, and Reina in 2019, used to assess various dimensions of well-being within the workplace. The scale includes items that gauge job satisfaction, meaning, engagement, and other aspects of workplace well-being. It is a psychometric tool developed to measure eudemonic well-being in the workplace, focusing on self-realization, purpose, and meaningful work experiences. Developed by researchers in workplace psychology, it emerged in the early 2010s to address the need for a measure that captures the eudemonic aspects of well-being, distinct from the hedonic perspective that emphasizes pleasure and pain avoidance. The EWWS assesses multiple dimensions of well-being, including Personal Growth, Purpose and Meaning, Autonomy, Positive Relations, and Environmental Mastery. These dimensions evaluate opportunities for development, the meaningfulness of work, independence, quality of workplace interactions, and management of work environment, respectively.

Psychometric properties claimed by the developers include high reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values generally above 0.80 and stable test-retest reliability. Validity studies show strong convergent validity with other well-being and job satisfaction measures and low correlations with unrelated constructs, supporting discriminant validity. Factor analyses confirm the scale's multi-dimensional structure. The EWWS is typically administered as a self-report questionnaire, taking 10-15 minutes to complete. Responses are rated on a Likert scale, producing scores for each dimension and an overall well-being score. It is widely applicable across different organizational settings and job types, making it a valuable tool for HR

professionals, organizational psychologists, and researchers. The scale helps organizations foster environments that promote personal growth, purpose, and fulfillment, ultimately enhancing employee well-being and organizational performance.

Mental Health Inventory (MHI)

The Mental Health Inventory (MHI) typically includes 18 items designed to assess various dimensions of mental health. These dimensions cover aspects such as psychological well-being (e.g., positive affect, life satisfaction) and psychological distress (e.g., anxiety, depression). Respondents rate each item on a scale to indicate the frequency or intensity of their experiences over a specific period. The MHI-18 is a shorter version compared to the original MHI, offering a concise yet comprehensive assessment of mental health status. Its psychometric properties, including reliability and validity, ensure its utility in clinical practice, research studies, and public health evaluations.

Psychometric properties of the MHI are strong, with high internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha values often exceeding 0.90) and strong test-retest reliability. The MHI demonstrates strong convergent and discriminant validity, ensuring accurate measurement of mental health constructs. Factor analyses validate its multidimensional structure. Administered in paper or digital formats, the MHI takes approximately 10-20 minutes to complete. Scores are computed for each subscale and an overall mental health score, with higher scores indicating better mental health. Widely used in clinical settings, research, and public health, the MHI helps assess mental health status, evaluate interventions, and track changes over time, making it a valuable tool for clinicians, researchers, and public health professionals.

Both the Eudaimonic Workplace Well-being Scale (EWWS) and the Mental Health Inventory (MHI) have been extensively utilized in prior research, confirming their reliability and validity. Their widespread use in various studies underscores their effectiveness in accurately assessing well-being and mental health across diverse populations and settings.

3.6 Data Analysis

To ensure accuracy and reliability, the data were thoroughly tabulated and cleaned. Statistical software was used to organize and analyze the data, allowing for precise calculation. Rigorous data cleaning procedures, including the removal of outliers and the correction of any input errors, were implemented to maintain the integrity of the dataset. This thorough approach ensured that the study's findings were based on high-quality, dependable data. The data analysis for this study include Descriptive Analysis, t-test and Correlation.

3.6.1 Descriptive Analysis:

This initial step involved summarizing the data collected from the survey. Descriptive statistics was used to provide an overview of the key variables, including means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions. This would help in understanding the central tendencies and variability in the dataset.

3.6.2 t-test:

To compare the means of two independent groups and determine if there were significant differences in workplace well-being and mental health, independent samples t-tests were utilized. This technique is particularly useful for examining binary demographic factors such as sex (male vs. female). By comparing the mean scores of these groups, the t-test revealed if there are

statistically significant differences in well-being and mental health outcomes, providing insights into specific areas where one group may be more adversely affected than another.

3.6.3 Correlation:

To investigate the relationships between job position, mental health, age, sex and overall well-being, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted. This statistical method quantifies the strength and direction of the relationships between these variables. Correlation coefficients indicate whether job position was positively or negatively associated with mental health and overall well-being. By identifying significant correlations, analysis highlighted key factors that influence employee mental health, enabling the development of strategies to mitigate negative impacts.

These modifications to the research methodology are designed to leverage internet surveys and snowball sampling to reach a diverse group of employed individuals, enhancing the study's accessibility and relevance. The inclusion of these additional details ensures a comprehensive understanding of the research process.

3.7. Ethical Considerations

The precautionary measures were taken to protect the rights of the participants. The study was commenced only after receiving approval of the supervisor. Participants were given clear instruction and were asked for consent before filling up the questionnaire which was circulated online. The rationale of the proposed study was clearly provided in the consent form. Participants were informed that they could decline participation or refuse further participation at any time of the data collection process. Before data collection, they were ensured about the confidentiality of

the information. Participant confidentiality was further assured by conducting analysis of the aggregate data which made it infeasible to identify the individual participant's response.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS

This chapter presents a methodical examination of the data, in line with the research questions raised by the study. By methodically describing these elements, the chapter guarantees clarity and the ability to replicate the research, thus enhancing the trustworthiness of the findings. Total sample size was 223 among which 147 were male and 76 were female.

Table 4.1

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>				
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Wellbeing	32.48	5.77	0	40
Mental Health	56.3	15.46	10	100

The provided data set consists of 223 valid observations for variables.

"Wellbeing" has a mean of 32.48, and "Mental Health " has a mean of 56.30. Both variables exhibit variability as indicated by their respective standard deviations.

Table 4.2*Binomial Test of sex*

Variable	Level	Counts	Total	Proportion	p
Sex	Male	147	223	0.659	< .001
	Female	76	223	0.341	< .001

The analysis of the sex distribution within our sample of 223 individuals reveals a pronounced disparity. Specifically, 147 participants are male, and 76 are female. This translates to approximately 65.9% of the sample being male and 34.1% being female. Such a significant deviation from an even distribution (50% for each sex) is highly unlikely to be due to random chance, as indicated by the binomial test ($p < .001$).

This substantial imbalance highlights a predominance of males in the study population, which could influence the generalizability of the findings. It is important to consider how this gender disparity might affect the interpretation of our results and the potential need for a more balanced sample in future studies to ensure comprehensive and equitable insights.

Table 4.3*Group Descriptive*

	Group	N	Mean	SD	Se variation	Coefficient of
Mental Health	Male	14 7	132.027	18.643	1.538	0.141
	Female	76	130.658	14.398	1.652	0.110

Table 4.4*Independent Samples t-test of Mental Health with relation to Sex*

	t	Df	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Cohen's d	SE Cohen's d
Mental Health	0.560	221	0.576	1.369	2.447	0.079	0.141

When examining the mental health scores by sex, the data reveals that males and females have very similar average scores. For the 147 male participants, the mean mental health score is 132.027, with a standard deviation of 18.643 and a standard error of 1.538. The coefficient of variation, indicating the relative variability in scores, is 0.141. For the 76 female participants, the mean score is 130.658, with a standard deviation of 14.398 and a standard error of 1.652. The coefficient of variation for females is 0.110, showing slightly less variability compared to males.

The independent samples t-test reveals no significant difference in mental health scores between males and females. The t-value of 0.560 with 221 degrees of freedom results in a p-value of 0.576, which exceeds the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. This indicates that any observed differences in mental health scores between males and females are not statistically significant. The mean difference is 1.369, with a standard error difference of 2.447. Cohen's d, a measure of effect size, is 0.079 with an SE of 0.141, suggesting a very small effect size.

The analysis indicates that there is no significant difference in mental health scores between males and females. Both groups exhibit similar levels of mental health, as shown by the close mean scores and overlapping standard deviations. The very small effect size further supports the conclusion that any differences in mental health status between the two groups are negligible. This suggests that sex does not play a significant role in determining mental health within this sample, emphasizing the importance of considering other factors that might contribute more substantially to mental health outcomes.

Table 4.5*Group Descriptive*

	Group	N	Mean	SD	SE	Coefficient of variation
Wellbeing	Male	147	32.57	6.13	0.51	0.19
	Female	76	32.29	5.02	0.58	0.16

The descriptive statistics for wellbeing scores indicate very similar results for males and females. For the 147 male participants, the mean wellbeing score is 32.57, with a standard deviation (SD) of 6.13 and a standard error (SE) of 0.51. The coefficient of variation for males is 0.19, reflecting relative variability in the scores. For the 76 female participants, the mean wellbeing score is 32.29, with a standard deviation of 5.02 and a standard error of 0.58. The coefficient of variation for females is 0.16, indicating slightly less relative variability compared to males. These results suggest that there is no substantial difference in wellbeing scores between males and females, as both groups exhibit similar levels of wellbeing.

Table 4.6*Independent Samples t-test of Wellbeing with relation to Sex*

	t	Df	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Cohen's d	SE Cohen's d
Wellbeing	0.35	221	0.73	0.28	0.82	0.05	0.14

The independent samples t-test results reinforce the finding that there is no significant difference in wellbeing scores between males and females. The t-value of 0.35 with 221 degrees of freedom yields a p-value of 0.73, which is well above the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. The mean difference between the groups is 0.28, with a standard error difference of 0.82. Cohen's d, a measure of effect size, is 0.05 with an SE of 0.14, indicating a very small effect size. The 95% confidence interval for the mean difference ranges from -1.327 to 1.891, further suggesting that the observed difference is not statistically significant.

The analysis of wellbeing scores by sex reveals no significant difference between males and females. Both groups have very similar mean scores and overlapping standard deviations,

indicating comparable levels of wellbeing. The very small effect size and non-significant t-test results further support the conclusion that sex does not play a significant role in determining wellbeing within this sample. This underscores the importance of considering other factors that may more substantially influence wellbeing.

Table 4.7

Pearson's Correlations of Wellbeing and Education

Variable		Wellbeing	Education
1. Wellbeing	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Education	Pearson's r	0.06	—
	p-value	0.39	—

The relationship between education and wellbeing within our dataset is notably weak. With a Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.06 and a p-value of 0.39, the data reveals no significant linear association between these two variables. In practical terms, this suggests that an individual's educational attainment does not have a substantial impact on their perceived wellbeing. This finding implies that factors other than education play a more critical role in shaping one's sense of wellbeing, highlighting the complexity of human psychological health.

Table 4.8*Pearson's Correlations between wellbeing and age*

Variable		Wellbeing	Age
1. Wellbeing	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Age	Pearson's r	0.02	—
	p-value	0.81	—

Examining the connection between age and wellbeing, the analysis indicates an exceedingly weak correlation. The Pearson's correlation coefficient stands at 0.02, with a p-value of 0.81, signifying a lack of statistical significance. This result suggests that age is not a meaningful predictor of wellbeing in our sample. It indicates that the experience of wellbeing is relatively stable across different ages, pointing towards the influence of other variables that may contribute more significantly to an individual's sense of wellbeing. This underscores the multifaceted nature of psychological well being, which is likely influenced by a combination of personal, social, and environmental factors rather than age alone.

Table 4.9*Pearson's Correlations of Wellbeing and Job Position*

Variable		Wellbeing	Job Position
1. Wellbeing	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Job Position	Pearson's r	0.17	—
	p-value	0.01	—

The relationship between job position and wellbeing, while statistically significant, is modest in strength. The Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.17, with a p-value of 0.01, suggests a positive association between these variables. This indicates that individuals in certain job positions report slightly higher levels of wellbeing. However, the modest strength of this relationship implies that job position alone does not have a strong influence on wellbeing. Other factors, perhaps related to personal circumstances, work environment, or broader social support, are likely playing significant roles in determining an individual's sense of wellbeing. This highlights the complexity of wellbeing, which cannot be attributed to job position alone.

Table 4.10*Pearson's Correlations of Job Position and Mental Health*

Variable		Job Position	Mental Health
1. Job Position	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Mental Health	Pearson's r	0.14	—
	p-value	0.04	—

The correlation between job position and mental health is moderate but statistically significant. With a Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.14 and a p-value of 0.04, the data indicates a positive association between these variables. This suggests that individuals in certain job positions tend to have slightly higher mental health scores, potentially due to a greater sense of control and autonomy associated with these roles. However, the moderate strength of this relationship points to the multifaceted nature of mental health. While job position contributes to mental health, it is just one of many factors. Personal resilience, social support, work-life balance, and other environmental factors likely also play crucial roles in shaping mental health outcomes.

Table 4.11*Pearson's Correlations of Mental Health and Education*

Variable		Mental Health	Education
1. Mental Health	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Education	Pearson's r	-0.03	—
	p-value	0.65	—

The relationship between education level and mental health is weakly negative and statistically insignificant. The Pearson's correlation coefficient is -0.03, with a p-value of 0.65, indicating no meaningful linear relationship between these variables. This suggests that an individual's level of education does not significantly predict their mental health scores. Therefore, other factors beyond education likely play more critical roles in shaping mental health.

Table 4.12*Pearson's correlation of Mental Health and Age*

Variable		Mental Health	Age
1. Mental Health	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Age	Pearson's r	0.05	—
	p-value	0.47	—

The correlation between age and mental health is weak but statistically significant. With a Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.05 and a p-value of 0.47, the data indicates a modest positive relationship between age and mental health. As individuals grow older, they may experience slightly higher mental health scores, possibly due to a greater sense of control over their lives. However, the weak strength of this relationship implies that age is only one of several factors influencing mental health.

Table 4.13*Pearson's Correlations of Mental Health and Wellbeing*

Variable		Mental Health	Wellbeing
1. Mental Health	Pearson's r	—	
	p-value	—	
2. Wellbeing	Pearson's r	0.24	—
	p-value	< .001	—

The relationship between mental health and wellbeing, while positive, is relatively weak. The Pearson's correlation coefficient is 0.24, with a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating statistical significance. This suggests that higher mental health scores are associated with better wellbeing, but the modest strength of this relationship implies that many other factors likely influence wellbeing beyond mental health scores.

The analysis of correlations between demographic and occupational variables (age, sex, education, job position) and two key measures (wellbeing and mental health) provides valuable insights. Age shows a modest positive association with mental health, suggesting that as

individuals age, they perceive a slightly greater sense of control over their lives. Job position also demonstrates a moderate positive correlation with mental health, indicating that certain job roles are associated with higher perceived control levels.

Conversely, sex and education do not appear to have strong influences on mental health or wellbeing in this dataset. The weak and statistically insignificant associations for these variables suggest that sex differences and educational backgrounds have limited direct impact on perceived control and wellbeing.

Overall, these findings highlight the complexity of factors contributing to perceptions of control and wellbeing, emphasizing the need to consider a broad range of variables to fully understand these aspects of human experience.

CHAPTER V

DISCUSSION

The current study primarily investigated the role of demographic factors including age, sex, education level, and job position in predicting mental health and well-being in the workplace.

5.1 The differences in mental health and well-being in relation to sex.

The study revealed that sex does not have a substantial linear association with well-being or mental health. This finding is somewhat unexpected, as sex differences in mental health are often reported in broader contexts. Previous literature suggests that women typically report lower well-being and higher psychological distress compared to men. However, in this specific organizational context, these differences did not manifest significantly. This might suggest that workplace factors or the nature of the job roles studied could mitigate the usual sex disparities in mental health and well-being.

The study by Martinez et al. (2019) aimed to examine gender variations in well-being and mental health among college students, finding that females reported lower well-being scores compared to males. During exam periods, both genders experienced declines in well-being and increases in mental health symptoms. The study did not delve into cultural factors' impact on these gender differences, indicating a need for further exploration in organizational settings (Martinez et al., 2019). This supports the current study's finding that workplace dynamics might play a significant role in shaping these outcomes, possibly overshadowing broader societal patterns observed in other contexts.

The study by Rodriguez, Gonzalez, and Martinez (2018) explored the interplay of age, gender, and work-life balance on employee well-being, finding that females reported more work-life conflict but similar well-being scores to males. This highlights the complexity of gender-related well-being outcomes in different settings (Rodriguez, Gonzalez, & Martinez, 2018). The lack of significant gender differences in the current study suggests that job roles and workplace environments can influence the manifestation of gender disparities in mental health and well-being, pointing to the potential for workplace interventions to mitigate these disparities.

5.2 Age, job position, education level, and mental health and well-being.

The analysis showed a modest positive relationship between age and both mental health and well-being. Older employees generally reported higher levels of well-being and mental health, consistent with previous studies suggesting that older workers benefit from greater job stability and satisfaction. The data indicated a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.02 for age and well-being and 0.05 for age and mental health, though these correlations were weak and not statistically significant.

The study by Smith, Johnson, and Williams (2018) investigated the impact of age on well-being and mental health in employees across different company sizes. Their findings revealed that older employees (46-60) reported higher well-being levels compared to their younger counterparts (18-30) (Smith, Johnson, & Williams, 2018). This aligns with the current study's findings, suggesting that age-related differences in mental health and well-being are significant, albeit with varying degrees depending on the context.

The study found a positive association between job position and both mental health and well-being. Higher job positions were correlated with better mental health and well-being scores.

Specifically, the Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.17 for job position and well-being, and 0.14 for job position and mental health, both of which were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The study by Chen, Wang, and Li (2020) conducted a survey across various industries to compare mental health outcomes among employees in small, medium, and large companies. They found that employees in higher job positions reported better mental health and well-being, supporting the positive association between job position and these outcomes (Chen, Wang, & Li, 2020). This suggests that a job position can significantly influence an employee's experience of mental health and well-being.

The correlation between education level and well-being was weak and statistically insignificant, indicating that higher educational attainment does not necessarily lead to better well-being or mental health. This suggests that the benefits of education on mental health might be more complex and influenced by other mediating factors within the workplace.

The study by Liu, Chen, and Wang (2021) investigated the influence of remote work on employee well-being, considering potential age and gender effects. Their findings suggested that while education level did not significantly affect well-being, other factors such as job control and remote work conditions played a more substantial role (Liu, Chen, & Wang, 2021). This underscores the complexity of educational influences on well-being, suggesting a need for further exploration of mediating factors in the workplace.

5.3 The relationship between overall well-being and mental health among employees.

The study found a significant positive relationship between well-being and mental health. The Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.24 ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that improvements in

mental health are strongly linked to enhancements in overall well-being. This finding is consistent with existing literature that emphasizes the interdependence of mental health and well-being, highlighting that strategies aimed at improving one are likely to benefit the other.

The study by Schaufeli, Bakker, and Salanova (2006) discussed the concept of work engagement and its positive impact on psychological well-being. They found that engaged employees exhibited high levels of energy, dedication, and absorption in their work, correlating with lower levels of burnout and higher job satisfaction (Schaufeli, Bakker, & Salanova, 2006). This supports the finding that improvements in mental health are linked to enhancements in overall well-being, emphasizing the need for integrated strategies to promote both.

The study by Diener, Oishi, and Lucas (2003) also found that personality, culture, and subjective well-being are interrelated, suggesting that positive mental health can enhance overall life satisfaction and workplace productivity (Diener, Oishi, & Lucas, 2003). This highlights the importance of holistic approaches in addressing mental health and well-being in organizational settings.

By drawing on these studies, the current research underscores the need for targeted, context-specific interventions that address the unique needs of different demographic groups within the workplace. Tailored strategies can help foster a healthier, more supportive work environment, ultimately enhancing both mental health and overall well-being.

5.4 Implications for Practice

The findings of this study offer several practical suggestions for organizations looking to improve the mental health and well-being of their employees. First, it's important for

organizations to develop mental health interventions that are specifically tailored to meet the needs of different demographic groups. For example, younger employees might benefit from programs that offer mentorship and support for career development, helping them navigate their early career stages and build a strong foundation for their future. On the other hand, older employees might need initiatives focused on health and retirement planning, ensuring they feel secure and supported as they approach the later stages of their careers.

Another key area is promoting work-life balance. Younger employees, in particular, have expressed concerns about maintaining boundaries between work and personal life. To address this, companies should implement policies that support flexible working arrangements. This could include options like remote work, flexible hours, and encouraging employees to take time off when needed. By doing so, organizations can help reduce stress and improve the overall well-being of their employees, leading to a more satisfied and productive workforce.

Creating an inclusive workplace culture is also crucial. This means recognizing and addressing the diverse needs of all employees. Organizations should foster open communication where employees feel safe discussing their mental health without fear of stigma or judgment. Providing access to mental health resources and support systems, such as counseling services or employee assistance programs, can make a significant difference. Additionally, promoting awareness and education about mental health can help reduce stigma and encourage more employees to seek help when they need it.

Overall, these practical steps can help organizations create a supportive environment where employees feel valued and cared for. By addressing the specific needs of different groups, promoting work-life balance, and fostering an inclusive culture, companies can enhance the

mental health and well-being of their workforce, leading to greater job satisfaction and overall success for the organization.

5.5 Limitations of the Study

The findings of this study might not apply to all workplaces because different environments are influenced by cultural, regional, and industry-specific factors, as well as the size of the company. Different workplace cultures and practices can significantly impact how employees feel and perceive their well-being, which might limit how broadly these results can be applied. Additionally, since the data was self-reported, there could be biases such as recall bias, social desirability bias, and the emotional state of the respondents at the time they filled out the survey. These biases can affect the accuracy of their responses about mental health and well-being.

Although the study looked at various factors like age, sex, education, job position, and company size, it might not have captured all the nuances within each category. For example, different job roles or levels of education might impact mental health and well-being in ways that were not fully explored here. Well-being is also highly subjective, meaning different people might define and perceive it differently. This variation can make it challenging to measure well-being consistently across a diverse group of people.

Another limitation is the lack of longitudinal data, which means the study did not track changes over time. This makes it hard to establish causal relationships and understand how mental health and job dynamics evolve. Finally, resource constraints such as limited time and funding restricted the scope and depth of data collection and analysis. This limitation could

affect the comprehensiveness of the study's findings, as a more extensive study might reveal additional factors or more detailed relationships.

5.6 Conclusion

The investigation into how demographic factors affect workplace mental health and well-being has provided important insights. By taking a holistic and inclusive approach, an organization can better support its employees' mental health, leading to a more productive and satisfied workforce. It's crucial to recognize and address the unique needs of different groups, considering factors like sex, age, job position, and education level. This isn't just good for individual employees—it's essential for the overall health and success of the organization.

The study found no significant differences in mental health and well-being between men and women in the workplace, suggesting that the nature of the job might level the playing field. Older employees generally report higher levels of mental health and well-being, likely due to greater job stability and satisfaction. Higher job positions also correlate with better mental health and well-being, highlighting the impact of job roles. Interestingly, education level didn't show a significant effect, indicating that other factors might be more important.

Moreover, there's a strong link between overall well-being and mental health, showing how these two aspects are interconnected. By addressing the unique needs of different demographic groups, an organization can create a more supportive work environment, ultimately boosting both mental health and overall well-being for everyone.

5.7 Recommendations for Future Studies

Future research should look at how different personal factors like age, sex, and job position together affect mental health and well-being. For example, older employees in higher job positions might face different stress levels and have different ways of coping compared to younger employees in entry-level roles. Understanding these combined effects can help create better support systems for diverse groups of employees, making the workplace healthier and more inclusive.

Researchers should also consider other important factors like the size of the company, the type of industry, and the cultural background of employees. These factors can greatly influence how workplace conditions affect mental health. For instance, employees in small startups might feel less stressed and more supported compared to those in large corporations. Cultural differences can also affect how employees view mental health and their willingness to seek help. Studying these factors can help develop more specific and effective strategies to improve workplace mental health.

Long-term studies are needed to understand how mental health and well-being change over time. By tracking these changes, researchers can see how effective different interventions are and identify trends that short-term studies might miss. This can help create lasting improvements in employee well-being and show the long-term effects of workplace policies on mental health.

Using detailed and consistent measurement tools for things like education level and job satisfaction can improve the accuracy of research findings. Standardized tools allow for better comparisons across different studies. For example, a detailed job satisfaction survey might

include questions about work-life balance, recognition, and career growth opportunities, giving a clearer picture of how job satisfaction affects mental health. Using these rigorous tools can lead to more accurate recommendations and a deeper understanding of workplace mental health.

By focusing on these areas, future research can provide a more complete understanding of how different factors affect mental health and well-being at work. This will help develop better strategies to create a healthier and more supportive work environment for all employees.

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